

INTERACTIVE METHODS FOR TEACHING ENGLISH IN THE KINDERGARTEN

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Annotation: *This article describes the strategies which are dedicated to the modern teaching English language through interactive methods in kindergarten. In this article, there are also several instructions which help to improve the efficiency of the lesson in kindergarten.*

Key words: *interactive methods, theoretical, practical parts, communication, interaction, second language, visual aids.*

Аннотация: *В данной статье описаны стратегии, посвященные современному обучению английскому языку интерактивными методами в детском саду. В этой статье также есть несколько инструкций, которые помогут повысить эффективность урока в детском саду.*

Ключевые слова: *интерактивные методы, теоретическая, практическая части, коммуникация, взаимодействие, второй язык, наглядные пособия*

In this day and age, English language plays an integral role in all spheres, namely, education, industries, politics, media, library, business, communication around the world and others. That is why, the popularity of both teaching and learning English language as a second language is increasing at an alarming rate. In recent years, there has been a growing interest in research in English, which is considered as the language of professional communication in different fields of activity. Thus, increasing enthusiasm for learning English is one of the most decisive tasks of a teacher. In fact, it is better to start learning a foreign language from a very young age. Because young children's brains continue to develop without stopping, they have the ability to absorb new information much faster than adults whose brains are fully formed. It is appropriate to plan a lesson taking into account these peculiarities. For example, the use of games, pictures, songs and poems, cartoons is an effective way to teach foreign language to children of preschool age. (1). If we want teach English to children of preschool, it requires plays, acts, songs, in general we should make learning a language a fun for them. Generally, we used to utilize the standard teaching of foreign languages. In other words, teachers always explain the themes, speak as well as show some cards in order to being understandable the information to children, otherwise, students listen, write all of the notes from the desks or whiteboards and memorize. At the end of the lessons, teachers give some quizzes and tests which are helpful to find out what the children have learned. This is called a passive teaching method, additionally, this method is also obsolete. But there is another method which is known as an active teaching method. It consists of a wider interaction of children not only with the teacher, but also with their pairs. During the interactive lessons, children work in small groups, create projects. If teachers only pay attention to the theoretical parts, the lesson will be boring, as a result, interests of children in learning English gradually decrease. That is why, we should take into account both practical and theoretical parts in equal. There are a lot of interactive methods.

Total Physical Response (TPR)

Total or full physical response method is widely used for working with children of kindergarten and primary school ages. Besides giving speeches by teachers in the classes, children take part into the learning processes by repeating words with various emotional shades, movements or dances during using this method. This strategy is universal, because we can use it for working with all types of learners, such as kinesthetic, visuals and auditory

learners. In this method, teacher explains the meaning of a new word through the movement of the body, then children should repeat after him during the period of pronouncing the studied word. For example, teacher introduces new word “to dance” to children. At first, guys ought to do what teacher says in English after explaining the word through the action of dancing by teacher. Secondly, the teacher shows the movement before children call it.

Working through visual aids, flashcards and objects

The age of preschool children is very important in learning something new, because their brain continue to develop without stopping. Additionally, preschoolers depend on their vision to learn tasks easily. If teachers use some pictures on cards or toys during teaching new vocabularies, it can be profitable for children in order to learn new words. For instance, when the theme is fruits, teachers should show the pictures of fruits to children and explain what kind of fruits they are, after that children repeat it again. Besides learning the name of fruits, children can simultaneously learn the colors by showing the fruits.

Musical chairs

After explanation of new theme, children should take some break. Instead of going out or doing something which is not important, playing “musical chairs” is the better option. In other words, if we, teachers, want to break the silence in the class, playing this game is the best way of making a lesson more interesting. This method is full of advantages. Firstly, it helps to improve coordination and motor skills for kids. It also gives a chance to enhance the level of listening of children. Kids can learn to practice listening and following instructions with pairs by having them assemble the chairs and listen to the game’s rules. They can test their attention throughout the game by seeing who notices when the music stops. Teachers can encourage kids to dance while they move around the chairs to the music or after they get out, which can help build bone strength. When the music stops, children can test their problem-solving skills by finding a chair before they’re all gone.

Hopscotch

Teachers can use this game to teach children new information or new words. Hopscotch can help kids learn to count to 10 by pairing counting with hopping through the spaces to make it fun. In addition to counting, children need to balance as they jump from square to square, especially if they hop on one foot. Hopscotch is an aerobic, bone-strengthening activity that can also help improve coordination, motor skills, and concentration. Children can play hopscotch alone or with a group. After they learn the rules, they can play it individually.

To sum up, we can make a lesson more interesting, and attract the attention of children with the help of interactive methods. So, through using these strategies, we can increase the effectiveness of the lesson, in addition to them, we encourage them to learn a foreign language in great detail.

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TABIATSHUNOSLIK DARSLARIDA AMALIY ISHAR SAMARADORLIGI

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Annotatsiya: Maqolada boshlang'ich sinf darslari jarayonida bolalarni tabiat bilan tanishtirishda amaliy ishlarni tashkil etishning samarali metodlari xususida fikr yuritilgan.

Tayanch tushunchalar: amaliy uslublar, retseptor, tajriba, obyekt, operatsiya, ekskursiya, gerbariy, granit, akvarium, terrarium.

Аннотация: В статье рассмотрены эффективные методы организации практической работы по приобщению детей к природе в процессе занятий в начальных классах.

Ключевые слова: Практические методы, рецептор, эксперимент, объект, операция, экскурсия, гербарий, гранит, аквариум, террариум.

Bolalarning bo'lajak kasbiy sifatlarini shakllantirishda nazariy bilimlar bilan bir qatorda amaliyot ham muhim o'rin egallaydi. Tabiiy ilmiy bilimlar uzoq yillar davomida amaliy faoliyat tufayli qo'lga kiritilgan. Atrof muhitni bilishda, anglashda ilmiy tajriba, amaliy bilimlar muhim rol o'ynab kelgan va kelmoqda. Ma'lumki, tabiatshunoslik keng qamrovli moddiy dunyoni rang-barang xususiyatlari, tabiatning har xil voqea hodisalarini o'rganuvchi fan bo'lib, ilmiy tajriba asosida shakllanadi, amaliyot esa mazkur fanning poydevori hisoblanadi. Insoniyatni tabiat qonunlari haqidagi bilimga asoslangan amaliy faoliyati bilish jarayonini, ilm- fan taraqqiyotini belgilaydi. Amaliyot - haqiqat mezonidir. Bilimlarga ehtiyoj amaliyotda tug'iladi va ularning to'g'riligi amaliyot orqali tekshiriladi hamda tasdiqlanadi. Bilim odamlar miyasida oz-o'zidan paydo bo'lmasdan, balki muayyan ish faoliyatida shakllanadi. Amaliyot insonni tabiat bilan munosabatida asosiy omil bo'lib, bu o'z navbatida, odamlarning o'zaro munosabatlari tizimida, ijtimoiy ishlab chiqarishda muhim rol o'ynaydi. Amaliyotning asosiy turlari moddiy ishlab chiqarish va ilmiy tajriba hisoblanadi. Ilmiy - tabiiy amaliyot quyidagi vazifalarni bajaradi.

1. Amaliyot bilish jarayonining rivojlantiruvchi omil. U nazariy bilimlarni umumlashtirib, ularni hayotiy jarayonlardan ajralishga yo'l qo'ymaydi.

2. Amaliyot bilishning buyurtmasi, ilovasi va maqsadi hamdir.

3. Amaliyot bilish jarayoninig haqiqiy ekanligini ko'rsatuvchi mezondir.

Tabiatshunoslikdagi amaliyot ilmiy ishlab chiqarishning asosiy omili bo'lib kelmoqda. Amaliyot nazariyani paydo bo'lishiga, ilmiy shakllanishiga va rivojlanishiga olib keladi. Bilishning aniqligi muayyan obekt haqidagi ma'lumotning haqiqat ekanligi bilan tasdiqlanadi. Ayni paytda, sharoit boshqacha bo'lsa, haqiqat ham boshqacha bo'lishi mumkin. Masalan, oddiy sharoit va bosimda suv 100C da qaynaydi. Lekin bosim o'zgarsa yoki og'ir suv bo'lsa, u aniq - konkret hisoblanadi.

Ma'lum tizimdagi haqiqat boshqa sharoitda butunlay o'zgarishi mumkin. G'oyaning amaliyotda tasdiqlanishi haqiqatning asosiy omili hisoblanadi. Amaliy ishlarga o'rgatish boshlang'ich sinflardan boshlanishi maqsadga muvofiqdir. Amaliy uslublar o'qituvchi tomonidan tashkil qilinadigan va yo'naltiriladigan, o'quvchilar fikrini rivojlantirishga mo'ljallagan so'z, ko'rgazmalilik va amaliy ishning o'zaro murakkab bog'lanishida bo'lishini ko'rsatadi. Amaliy uslublar qo'llanilishi bolalar retseptorlari va effektorlarining jadal faoliyati bilan bog'liq. Amaliy uslublar o'rganilgan materialni chuqur tushunib yetishga, ko'nikma va malakalar hosil qilishga imkoniyat yaratadi. Amaliy uslublarni qo'llashga o'quvchilar faoliyatining o'zi, bilim manbai hisoblanadi. Bunday usullar sirasiga og'zaki, yozma mashqlar, laboratoriya ishlari, maktab yer maydoni, tirik tabiat burchagida, sinfdan tashqari bajariladigan mashg'ulotlar kiradi.

Amaliy uslublarning turlariga:

1. Bolalarning tarqatma didaktik material bilan turli narsalar yasashi;
2. Rasm chizishi;
3. Tabiat obyektlarini tanib olish va aniqlash bo'yicha ishlari;
4. Hodisalarni kuzatish va qayd qilishlari;